

RECENT SOLAR CAR TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENTS INCLUDING
AUSTRALIAN WORLD SOLAR CHALLENGE RESULTS

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ABSTRACT

The results of the GM Sunrayce USA and 1990 World Solar Challenge will be presented. It will include solar array measurements, performance data and vehicle specifications, as well as highlights of the two events. Plans for the next intercollegiate solar car race sponsored by the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE), called Sunrayce '93, will be updated. Results of an economic assessment of PV-assisted electric cars is also summarized.

INTRODUCTION

Three years ago at the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference held in Las Vegas, the GM Sunraycer was displayed and the team proudly described their accomplishments in the 1987 World Solar Challenge. Since then much has happened. GM Sunrayce USA was announced three months later. Within a year and a-half, thirty-two of North America's best universities built solar cars and, in July 1990, raced from Florida to Detroit. Four months after that, six of the best Sunrayce teams, including the three winners, traveled to Darwin to race across the Australian continent against thirty-two international competitors in the 1990 World Solar Challenge. In the mean time, the first PV-assisted electric cars in the U.S. were being used to compete in the American Tour de Sol. And in late 1990, a preliminary costing model for PV modules used on electric cars was completed that shows cases that are cost effective. (1) Will photovoltaics effect the way automotive engineering is approached in the future? Some say it already has.

GM SUNRAYCE USA

In July 1990, thirty-two North American university teams gathered in Orlando, Florida to compete in GM Sunrayce USA, a 1644 mile transcontinental race of solar powered cars. Using only sunlight for power, the cars had to travel through eight states over eleven days before

reaching the finish line in Detroit, Michigan. Created as a student competition to strengthen hands-on science and engineering skills, Sunrayce was a triumph to higher learning. What started out as a race of students ended as a race of scientists and engineers well prepared for their future.

The prize for the three winners of Sunrayce was an all expense paid trip to compete in the 1990 Australian World Solar Challenge (WSC). The WSC is a 1870 mile solar car race across the Australian continent that stretched from Darwin to Adelaide. This year's event had thirty-six competitors from around the world, including eleven entries from Japan, eight from the U.S., and five from Europe. In total, sixty-two different solar racing teams competed in these two events in 1990.

Sunrayce 1990 was won by the team from the University of Michigan. Their "Sunrunner" was impressive. Painted bright yellow, it was a well designed and reliable solar car. The Michigan team drove Sunrunner the entire distance from Florida to Detroit, and then from Darwin to Adelaide, without a design failure of any kind. Its powerful 1140 watt array provided enough energy to maintain steady speeds of 35 to 40 miles per hour under mid-day sunlight.

In second place was a cleverly designed car by the team from Western Washington University, called "Viking XX". They used their solar array to maximum advantage by including as part of their design strategy the ability to drive the car in two directions. Its large slanted array was fixed at approximately 15 degrees from the horizontal. At noon, the car was turned around and driven backwards so that the array would be pointed toward the western sky. This enabled the solar array to face the sun more directly for longer periods of the day. The team originally built their solar array out of hundreds of 14% terrestrial grade cells which generated 1560 watts of electricity under full

sunlight. After winning Sunrayce, the team built a new solar array made out of 17-18% aerospace grade cells which generated 1683 watts of electricity in Australia.

Viking XX achieved the highest recorded speed during Sunrayce. It was clocked at 54 mph at Indianapolis Speedway during the eighth day of the race. The University of Maryland's "Pride of Maryland", which placed third overall, achieved the second highest recorded speed. The Pride of Maryland was clocked at 52 mph at Daytona Speedway to win the pole position for the start of Sunrayce.

WORLD SOLAR CHALLENGE (WSC)

The 1990 WSC was won by "The Spirit of Biel" from the Engineering University of Biel, in Switzerland. Biel's winning time was 46 hours and eight minutes (40.6 ave. mph), one hour and 14 minutes behind Sunraycer's record established in 1987 (41.7 ave. mph). Biel's array was comprised of laser grooved aerospace cells that were connected by overlapping them in shingle style. The combination of high-efficiency cells with a high packing density (97.5%) resulted in an impressive 170 watts per square meter. The sleek, colorful, 401 lb solar racing car was clocked at 63 mph during qualification trials and cruised at 45 mph under mid-day sun.

Second place was captured by an entry from Japan's Honda Corporation. This immaculate, well engineered car was similar in shape to GM's Sunraycer, but with more frontal area. Named "Dream" after the first Honda motorcycle, it was the pre-race favorite because of its huge corporate backing and impressive statistics (304 lbs, 45-48 mph cruising speeds). However, Honda used a relatively small battery and was unable to keep up with the Spirit of Biel under the heavy cloud conditions experienced during the first day of the race.

Michigan's Sunrunner won the third place trophy. The Sunrunner team raced consistently and reliably, just like they did in Sunrayce. Their accomplishment was not easy though. Viking XX and "Phoebus III", an entry built by a Japanese team from the Hoxan solar cell company, were very close the entire race. Sunrunner crossed the finish line with Phoebus III less than five minutes behind them!

A total of six university teams that were in Sunrayce traveled to Australia to compete in the WSC. All of them placed in the top eleven out of a field of thirty-six international competitors. Performance statistics from both races are contained in Tables 1 and 2. The first and second place winning solar cars from each race are shown in Figures 1-4.

Hans Tholstrup, Director of the World Solar Challenge, said in an article in the November 26th, 1990 issue of Australia's *Time* magazine that the World Solar Challenge was the most important race in the world. He calls solar car racing "brain sport" because it is a race of scientists using concepts and technologies slightly ahead of their time. They also help educate the world that there are alternatives, so I think of it as "racing for the future."

SUNRAYCE '93

On August 19, 1991, the DOE announced Sunrayce '93, an intercollegiate competition of solar-powered cars. Sunrayce '93 is being instituted as an ongoing educational program that will culminate every two years with a cross-country race. The first race will be held June 20-26, 1993, to coincide with the week of the summer solstice. It will start in Texas and finish approximately 1600 kilometers (1000 miles) later in Minnesota. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, the National Renewable Energy Laboratory, the Society of Automotive Engineers, and General Motors Corporation will join DOE in sponsoring and organizing the event. This program is open exclusively to colleges, universities, trade schools, and other higher educational institutions in North America. Up to 36 schools will be selected to participate in the 1993 event based on a proposal selection process.

GM Sunrayce USA was the first intercollegiate solar car race held in North America. Based on the students' outstanding accomplishments in building their solar cars and the success of this design competition in motivating students to apply math, science, and engineering skills to the solar car challenge, an expanded program is being instituted. DOE is repeating this exciting educational experience as part of a long-term commitment to support science education, strengthen our Nation's

TABLE 1

GM SUNRAYCE USA VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS

POS	SCHOOL NAME	WEIGHT (lbs/kgs)	SOLAR ARRAY		BATTERIES		
			Power (watts)	Manf.	Size (kWhr)	Type	Manf.
1	Michigan	575/261	1140	Spectrolab	4.9	Eagle Picher	AgZn
2	West Wash	646/293	1560	Siemens	4.4	Eagle Picher	AgZn
3	Maryland	415/188	1230	Solarex	4.2	Yardney	AgZn
4	L.A.	507/230	900	Spectrolab	5.0	Eagle Picher	AgZn
5	Crowder	569/258	1230	Siemens	5.0	Eagle Picher	AgZn
6	MIT	377/171	580	Astropower	4.9	Yardney	AgZn
7	Stanford	600/272	840	Siemens	5.0	Saft	AgZn
8	WMU/Jordan	542/246	780	Siemens	4.9	Yardney	AgZn
9	Colorado	559/254	840	Siemens	4.7	Saft	AgZn
10	Pomona	520/236	800	ASEC	4.7	Yardney	AgZn
11	Drexel	424/192	610	Siemens	2.7	Eagle Picher	AgZn
12	RIT	434/197	670	Spectrolab	3.6	Yardney	AgZn
13	Stark	684/310	640	Siemens	4.7	Eagle Picher	AgZn
14	WPI	450/204	630	Mobil Solar	5.0	BST	AgZn
15	Auburn	710/322	720	Astropower	4.9	Yardney	AgZn
16	Mankato	820/372	1100	Siemens	3.3	GNB	Pb/A
17	Iowa State	550/249	690	Siemens	3.1	Eagle Picher	AgZn
18	N. Texas	376/171	430	Astropower	2.0	Farradane	Pb/A
19	Northridge	459/208	890	Siemens	1.8	Farradane	Pb/A
20	Rose Hulman	326/148	950	Siemens	3.2	Eagle Picher	AgZn
21	Obispo	610/277	850	Westinghouse	3.0	Yardney	AgZn
22	Texas	340/154	640	Siemens	1.9	Eagle Picher	Ni/H2
23	Dartmouth	718/326	590	Siemens	3.3	GNB	Pb/A
24	Waterloo	546/248	860	Siemens	5.0	Eagle Picher	AgZn
25	FIT	541/245	640	Spectrolab	4.9	Eagle Picher	AgZn
26	Penn	609/276	570	ASEC	2.6	Panasonic	Pb/A
27	VPI	647/293	430	ASEC	3.5	Yardney	AgZn
28	Clarkson	555/252	570	Solec	2.9	Eagle Picher	AgZn
29	Ottawa	600/272	570	Siemens	5.0	JCI	ZnBr
30	Puerto Rico	805/365	850	Solarex	2.9	Eagle Picher	AgZn
31	Arizona	650/295	480	Siemens	5.0	Trojan Pacer	Pb/A
32	Villanova	639/290	340	Solarex	4.0	Eagle Picher	AgZn

Battery Key: AgZn = Silver Zinc
Pb/A = Lead Acid
Ni/H2 = Nickel Hydrogen
ZnBr = Zinc Bromide

TABLE 2
1990 AUSTRALIAN WORLD SOLAR CHALLENGE
VEHICLE SPECIFICATIONS

POS NO.	TEAM NAME	ARRAY POWER		WEIGHT lbs/kgs	BATTERY (kWhr)
		(watts)	Manuf.		
1	100 Biel	1300	Telefunken	402/183	4.6 AgZn
2	1 Honda	1100	Hoxan	304/138	1.9 AgZn
3	35 Michigan	1140	Spectrolab	505/229	4.0 AgZn
4	6 Hoxan	1100	Hoxan	359/163	1.9 AgZn
5	20 West Wash	1683	Spectrolab	574/260	4.1 AgZn
6	30 AERL	1026	Solarex	373/169	1.5 Pb/A
7	10 Maryland	1242	Solarex	390/177	2.9 AgZn
8	33 Crowder	1230	ASEC	549/249	4.6 AgZn
9	9 Barossa	900	BP Solar	551/250	2.7 AgZn
10	19 Cal St L.A.	862	Spectrolab	452/205	3.0 AgZn
11	25 Pamona	980	ASEC	456/207	2.8 AgZn
12	15 N. T. Univ.	927	ASEC	369/167	4.8 AgZn
13	12 Monash Univ.	776	Helios	456/207	1.7 AgZn
14	77 Kyocera	990	Kyocera	340/154	2.2 NiZn
15	22 Trykowski	600	Kyocera	718/326	4.8 Pb/A
16	17 Simon	870	Showa -ARCO	413/187	1.7 Pb/A
17	14 Lajovic	700	Showa-ARCO	313/142	1.0 AgZn
18	4 Hawaii H.S.	700	Photocom	357/162	2.2 Pb/A
19	8 Dripstone H.S.	750	ARCO	496/225	1.5 Pb/A
20	18 Annesley	900	Showa-ARCO	617/280	1.6 Pb/A
21	2 Sofix	900	Sharp	411/186	2.9 NiZn
22	29 Waseda	880	Showa-ARCO	344/156	0.5 Pb/A
23	898 Stewart Lister	740	Solarex	564/256	2.1 Pb/A
24	28 Queens Univ.	860	Astropower	576/261	2.0 AgZn
25	83 AISOL	700	Sharp	700/317	2.0 NiZn
26	26 Yamawaki	740	Kyocera	320/145	1.1 NiZn
27	90 Barclay	700	BP Solar	628/285	none!
28	5 SEL	600	SEL a-Si	411/186	1.2 Pb/A
29	21 Helio Det	600	AEG	265/120	1.2 Pb/A
30	92 Solar Japan	600	Sharp	386/175	1.0 Pb/A
31	23 Denmark	950	Helios	483/219	2.4 AgZn
32	11 Morphett H.S.	900	Showa-ARCO	304/138	1.0 Pb/A
33	16 England	800	BP Solar	459/208	4.2 Pb/A
34	101 Hosokawa	500	Sharp	291/132	1.0 Pb/A
35	27 Mark Jensen	500	BP Solar	591/268	2.8 Pb/A
36	31 U. of Oklahoma	800	Siemens	584/265	1.9 Pb/A

Battery Key: AgZn = Silver Zinc
Pb/A = Lead Acid
NiZn = Nickel Zinc

Figure 1. Michigan's "Sunrunner"
1st place, GM Sunrayce USA

Figure 2. "Viking XX"
2nd place, GM Sunrayce USA

Figure 3. "Sprit of Biel"
1st place, 1990 WSC.

Figure 4. Honda's "Dream"
2nd place, 1990 WSC.

Figure 5. Solar Car Corporation's PV-assisted electric vehicle.

international competitive position, and develop clean, efficient energy alternatives.

The theme of Sunrayce '93 is "Education, Energy, and the Environment." The goal is to make science education exciting. Accordingly, we hope that Sunrayce '93 will provide hundreds of students throughout North America the chance to challenge the future "hands-on," to display their efforts to the public, and to receive recognition for their accomplishments.

PV-ASSISTED ELECTRIC VEHICLES

Solar car competitions not only provide educational benefits and increase public awareness of the potential of solar energy, but the advanced technologies are directly applicable to passenger electric vehicles. For example, the same engineers that designed and built the Sunraycer, which won the 1987 World Solar Challenge, are now designing and building GM's new Impact electric vehicle.

Is the use of photovoltaics on a passenger electric vehicle (see Figure 5) economically viable? To answer that question the DOE contracted JPL to conduct a study to assess the feasibility and calculate the payback periods of

adding PV modules to an electric vehicle.(1) A computer model was generated that looked at 3240 different cases. It included eight locations, three array types, three vehicle types, three battery types, five vehicle use patterns and three electricity rates. In certain cases, such as in sunny regions where the vehicle is parked outside, the payback period occurs in less than one year. Obviously, if you drive only at night or park in an underground parking lot, there is no payback.

The largest cost driver in this application is battery life extension. If you can increase the life of a \$1200 battery pack from two to four years it will quickly pay for a \$600 PV array. The study also found that the harder the car is driven the better the payback. There is less economic value to the application if you drive 15 miles or less each day because with light use the batteries last longer and the solar array isn't used to its full capacity. The best payback resulted in cases where the car was driven 50 miles or more.

REFERENCE

1. Wally E. Rippel. "Viability Study of Photo-Voltaic Systems Added to Terrestrial Electric Vehicles, JPL D-7824, September, 1990.